

Ehrenfest's Theorem and Newton's Equations

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Ehrenfest's theorem, which has the appearance of Newton's equations in a sense i.e. $d/dt \langle x \rangle = \langle p \rangle$ and $d/dt \langle p \rangle = \langle -dV/dx \rangle$, is often used to link quantum and classical mechanics. In this note, we argue that the d/dt used in the theorem is really d/dt (partial) because $\langle \rangle$ removes all x dependence. We argue that this is a problem because Newton's second law $dp/dt = F = -dV/dx$ is equivalent to $dp/dx v = F$ which leads to a conservation of energy law and is local. As a result, we argue that to find a link with Newtonian physics one should seek local quantum expressions which are associated with both dp/dt and energy conservation. Such a connection is already present in bound state quantum mechanics which yields $0=0$ for Ehrenfest's theorem for an energy eigenstate. The energy eigenstate nevertheless is as valid a state as any to be compared with Newtonian mechanics. Thus we use a different approach to compare quantum bound states with classical physics and find that it is $prms$ which is important in the equation $dp/dt = -dV/dx$ and that this relationship holds locally. It seems Ehrenfest's theorem uses $\langle \rangle$ with d/dt (partial) in order to obtain commutation relationships between $H = pp/2m + V(x)$ and p or x which in turn yield $-dV/dx$ or p so we argue that $d/dt \langle \rangle$ is not the same as d/dt in classical physics which acts both as d/dt partial as well acting on x as in $dp/dt = dp/dx v$.

Ehrenfest's Theorem

In (1) Ehrenfest's theorem is given as:

$$d/dt \langle p \rangle = \langle -dV/dx \rangle \quad ((1a)) \quad \text{and} \quad m \, d/dt \langle x \rangle = \langle p \rangle \quad ((1b))$$

These have the appearance of Newtonian equations i.e. $dp/dt = -dV/dx$ and $m \, dx/dt = p$ with two exceptions. First, average values over all space are used in Ehrenfest's theorem and secondly d/dt is really d/dt (partial) while Newton's equations use d/dt total i.e. $dp/dt = dp/dx v$. In particular, d/dt partial used in the theorem is applied to $W^*(x,t)$ and $W(x,t)$ (W =wavefunction) in $\langle \rangle$ in order to pull out the operator $H = pp/2m + V(x)$. This then leads to a commutation relation with x and p . In the case of p , it is an operator $-id/dx$ which converts $V(x)$ to $-dV/dx$ and in the case of pp and x one obtains p . Thus we argue that ((1a)) and ((1b)) only give a superficial appearance of Newton's law. They yield $\langle -dV/dx \rangle$ and $\langle p \rangle$, but the left hand side is not the Newtonian result. Furthermore, ((1a)) and ((1b)) yield zero for a bound eigenstate because $\langle p \rangle$ and $\langle x \rangle$ are not time dependent i.e. $\exp(-iEnt)\exp(iEnt)$, but there is no reason why a bound eigenstate should not be linked to classical mechanics if other quantum situations are, as is the understanding of the theorem.

Bound Quantum Eigenstates

As a result of issues outlined in the previous section, we seek a scenario based on bound eigenstates which is linked to Newton's equations locally. In particular, we wish to have d/dt be a total time derivative. At first this seems like a problem because bound states are associated with

the time-independent Schrodinger equation which does not explicitly contain time. This, however, is not a problem as $dp/dt = dp/dx v$ in Newtonian mechanics, so time does not have to appear explicitly .

Furthermore it follows from Newtonian mechanics that $dp/dx v = F$ which means one may also obtain a conservation of energy statement for conservative forces i.e.

$$p^2/2m + V(x) = E \quad ((2))$$

((2)) is as fundamental as $dp/dt = -dV/dx$ and so we wish to find a quantum scheme which involves both. In classical physics, p which appears in ((2)) is identical to the p in $dp/dt = F$. Quantum mechanics, however, uses averages, both locally and over space i.e. $\langle \rangle$. ((2)) seems to imply that an average of $p^2/2m$ is important, but this leads to an issue as p_{rms} is not the same as p_{ave} locally i.e.

$$p_{ave} = [-idW/dx / W] \quad ((3a)) \quad \text{while} \quad [p^2]_{ave} = [-1/2m d/dx dW/dx]/W \quad ((3b))$$

((3a)) is not equivalent to the square root of ((3b)). We argue that one should retain ((3b)) if one wishes to retain ((2)). How does $dp/dt = F$ enter in such a case?

It enters through the use of p_{rms} in place of p_{ave} . In other words, the time independent Schrodinger equation is equivalent to energy conservation i.e. ((2))

$$[-1/2m d/dx dW/dx]/W + V(x) = E \quad ((4)) \quad \text{and}$$

$$d p_{rms}/dx \quad v_{rms} = -dV/dx \quad ((6))$$

((6)) is equivalent to $dp/dt = dp/dx v = F$, so using p_{rms} allows for a link to both ((2)) and $dp/dt = F$. As a result, we suggest that this is the approach to use to display a relationship between quantum and classical mechanics.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that although the Ehrenfest theorem has the appearance of Newton's second law: $d/dt \langle p \rangle = \langle -dV/dx \rangle$ with $dp/dt = -dV/dx$, it is nonlocal i.e. $\langle \rangle$ implies an integral over all space, d/dt is the partial time derivative and not the full as in the classical case and it does not yield a result for a bound eigenstate other than $0=0$. It seems that d/dt which is really d/dt partial in the theorem is used to operate on W^* and W (wavefunctions) which in turn leads to commutation relations with $H = p^2/2m + V$ and p and x . In other words, it is a mathematical procedure used to create dV/dx and p through commutation and the operator form for p i.e. $-id/dx$.

We argue that a link between quantum mechanics and Newtonian mechanics should be associated with both $E = p^2/2m + V(x)$ and $dp/dt = F$ because both are equivalent classical forms. Quantum mechanics, however, uses averages which implies an average of $p^2/2m$ i.e. $[-1/2m d/dx dW/dx]/W$ or $p_{rms} p_{rms} / 2m$. As a result, in order to have quantum mechanics (for a bound eigenstate) yield conservation of energy and $dp/dt = F$, one must substitute p with p_{rms} . In such a

case, one uses $dp/dt = dp/dx v$ and so time does not appear explicitly. The quantum time independent equation is $[-1/2m d/dx dW/dx]/W + V = E$ which is already a conservation of energy equation so taking d/dx of both sides yields Newton's second law, but with p replaced with $prms$. We argue that this is an approach which links quantum mechanics to classical Newtonian physics.

References

1. https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Ehrenfest_theorem